

1 Article

2 The Cosine Measure of Single Valued 3 Neutrosophic Multisets for Multiple Attribute 4 Decision-Making

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12 **Abstract:** Based on the multiplicity evaluation in some real situations, this paper firstly
13 introduces a single valued neutrosophic multiset (SVNM) as a subclass of neutrosophic
14 multiset (NM) to express the multiplicity information and the operational relations of
15 SVNMs. Then, a cosine measure between SVNMs and weighted cosine measure between
16 SVNMs are presented to measure the cosine degree between SVNMs, and their properties are
17 investigated. Based on the weighted cosine measure of SVNMs, a multiple attribute
18 decision-making method under a SVNM environment is proposed, in which the evaluated
19 values of alternatives are taken the form of SVNMs. The ranking order of all alternatives and
20 the best one can be determined by the weighted cosine measure between every alternative
21 and the ideal alternative. Finally, an actual application on the selecting problem illustrates the
22 effectiveness and application of the proposed method.

23 **Keywords:** single valued neutrosophic set (SVNS); neutrosophic multiset (NM); single
24 valued neutrosophic multiset (SVNM); cosine measure; multiple attribute decision-making.

26 1. Introduction

27 In 1965, Zadeh [1] proposed the theory of fuzzy sets (FS), in which every fuzzy element is
28 expressed by the membership degree $T(x)$ belonging to the scope of $[0, 1]$. While the fuzzy
29 membership degree of $T(x)$ is difficult to be determined, or can't be expressed by an exact
30 real number, the practicability of FS is limited. In order to avoid the above situation, Turksen [2]
31 extended a single value membership to an interval-valued membership. Generally, when the
32 membership degree $T(x)$ is determined, the non-membership degree can be calculated by $1 -$
33 $T(x)$. Considering the role of the non-membership degree, Atanassov [3] put forward the
34 intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFS) and introduced the related theory of IFS. Then IFS has been
35 widely used for solving the decision-making problems. Although the FS theory and IFS theory
36 have been constantly extended and completed, they are not applicable to all the fuzzy
37 problems. In 1998, Smarandache [4] added the uncertain degree to the IFS and put forward the
38 theory of neutrosophic set (NS), which is a general form of the FS and IFS. NS is composed of

39 the neutrosophic components of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity denoted by T , I , F ,
 40 respectively. Since then, many forms of neutrosophic set were proposed as extension of the
 41 neutrosophic set. Wang and Smarandache [5-6] introduced a single valued neutrosophic set
 42 (SVNS) and an interval neutrosophic set (INS). Smarandache [7] and Smarandache and Ye [8]
 43 presented **n-value and** refined-single valued neutrosophic sets (R-SVNSs). Fan and Ye [9]
 44 presented a refined-interval neutrosophic set (R-INS). Ye [10] presented a dynamic single
 45 valued neutrosophic multiset (DSVM), and so on.

46 Now, more researches have been done on the NS theory by experts and scholars. Ye [11-12]
 47 proposed the correlation coefficient and the weighted coefficient correlation of SVNS and
 48 proved that cosine similarity is a special case of the SVNS correlation coefficient. Broumi and
 49 Smarandache [13] proposed three vector similarity methods to simplify the similarity of SVNS,
 50 including Jaccard similarity, Dice similarity, and cosine similarity. Majumdar and Samanta [14]
 51 gave the similarity formula of SVNSs. Broumi and Smarandache [15] gave the correlation
 52 coefficient of INSs. Based on **the Hamming and Euclidean distances**, Ye [16] defined similarity
 53 of INSs. For the operation rules of NSs, Smarandache, Ye and Chi [4, 16, 17] gave different
 54 operation rules, respectively, they all have certain rationality and applicability.

55 Recently, Smarandache [18] introduced the neutrosophic multiset and the neutrosophic
 56 multiset algebraic structures, in which one or more elements are repeated times keeping the
 57 same or different neutrosophic components. Its concept is different from the concept of single
 58 valued neutrosophic multiset in [10, 19]. Till now, there are few studies and applications of
 59 neutrosophic multisets (NM) in science and engineering fields, so we introduce a single valued
 60 neutrosophic multiset (SVNM) as a **subclass** of neutrosophic multiset (NM) to express the
 61 multiplicity information and propose a decision-making methods based on the weighted
 62 cosine measures of SVNMs, and then provide a decision-making example to show its
 63 application under SVNM environments.

64 The rest sections of this article are organized as follows. Section 2 describes some basic
 65 concepts of SVNS, NM and the cosine measure of SVNSs. Section 3 presents a SVNM and its
 66 basic operational relations. Section 4 proposes a cosine measure between SVNMs and a
 67 weighted cosine measure between SVNMs and investigates their properties. Section 5
 68 establishes a multiple attribute decision-making method using the weighted cosine measure of
 69 SVNMs under SVNM environment. Section 6 presents an actual example to demonstrate the
 70 application of the proposed methods under SVNM environment. Section 7 gives a conclusion
 71 and further research.

72 2. Some Concepts of SVNS and NM

73 **Definition 1. [5]** Let X be a space of points (objects), with a generic element x in X . A SVNS R in X
 74 can be characterized by a truth-membership function $T_R(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership
 75 function $I_R(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_R(x)$, where $T_R(x), I_R(x), F_R(x) \in [0,1]$ for each
 76 point x in X . Then, a SVNS R can be expressed by the following form:

$$77 R = \{(x, T_R(x), I_R(x), F_R(x)) | x \in X\}.$$

78 Thus, the SVNS R satisfies the condition $0 \leq T_R(x) + I_R(x) + F_R(x) \leq 3$.

79 **For two SVNSs M and N , the relations of them are defined as follows [5]:**

- 80 (1) $M \subseteq N$ if and only if $T_M(x) \leq T_N(x)$, $I_M(x) \geq I_N(x)$, $F_M(x) \geq F_N(x)$ for any x in X ;
 81 (2) $M = N$ if and only if $M \subseteq N$ and **$N \subseteq M$** ;
 82 (3) $M^c = \{(x, F_M(x), 1 - I_M(x), T_M(x)) | x \in X\}$.

83 In order to writing convenience, an element (called single-valued neutrosophic number
84 (SVNN) in the SVNS R can be denoted by $R = \langle T_R(x), I_R(x), F_R(x) \rangle$ for any x in X . For two
85 SVNNs M and N , the operational relations of them can be defined as follows [5]:

$$86 \quad (1) \quad M \cup N = \langle \max(T_M(x), T_N(x)), \min(I_M(x), I_N(x)), \min(F_M(x), F_N(x)) \rangle \text{ for any } x \text{ in } X;$$

$$87 \quad (2) \quad M \cap N = \langle \min(T_M(x), T_N(x)), \max(I_M(x), I_N(x)), \max(F_M(x), F_N(x)) \rangle \text{ for any } x \text{ in } X.$$

88 For two SVNNs M and N , the operational rules of them can be defined as follows [5]:

$$89 \quad M+N = \langle T_M(x) + T_N(x) - T_M(x)T_N(x), I_M(x)I_N(x), F_M(x)F_N(x) \rangle \text{ for any } x \text{ in } X; \quad (1)$$

$$90 \quad M \times N = \langle T_M(x)T_N(x), I_M(x) + I_N(x) - I_M(x)I_N(x), F_M(x) + F_N(x) - F_M(x)F_N(x) \rangle \text{ for any } x \text{ in}$$

$$91 \quad X; \quad (2)$$

$$92 \quad \varphi M = \langle 1 - (1 - T_M(x))^\varphi, (I_M(x))^\varphi, (F_M(x))^\varphi \rangle \text{ for } \varphi > 0 \text{ and any } x \text{ in } X; \quad (3)$$

$$93 \quad M^\varphi = \langle (T_M(x))^\varphi, (1 - I_M(x))^\varphi, (1 - F_M(x))^\varphi \rangle, \text{ for } \varphi > 0 \text{ and any } x \text{ in } X. \quad (4)$$

94 **Definition 2 [20].** Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ be a space of points (objects), L and M be two SVNSs. The
95 cosine measure between L and M is defined as follows:

$$96 \quad \rho(L, M) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} (|T_L(x_i) - T_M(x_i)| + |I_L(x_i) - I_M(x_i)| + |F_L(x_i) - F_M(x_i)|) \right\} \quad (5)$$

97 Obviously, the cosine measure between L and M satisfies the following properties [20]:

$$98 \quad \textcircled{1} \quad 0 \leq \rho(L, M) \leq 1;$$

$$99 \quad \textcircled{2} \quad \rho(L, M) = 1 \text{ if and only if } L = M;$$

$$100 \quad \textcircled{3} \quad \rho(L, M) = \rho(M, L).$$

101 **Definition 3 [18].** Let X be a space of points (objects), and a neutrosophic multiset is repeated by one or
102 more elements with the same or different neutrosophic components.

103 For example, $M = \{(m_1, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (m_2, \langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.1 \rangle), (m_3, \langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.2 \rangle)\}$ is a
104 neutrosophic set rather than a neutrosophic multiset; while $K =$
105 $\{(k_1, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (k_1, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (k_1, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (k_2, \langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.1 \rangle)\}$ is a neutrosophic
106 multiset, where the element k_1 is repeated. Then we can say that the element k_1 has
107 neutrosophic multiplicity 3 with the same neutrosophic components.

108 While $L = \{(l_1, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (l_1, \langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle), (l_1, \langle 0.8, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle), (l_2, \langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.1 \rangle)\}$ is also a
109 neutrosophic multiset since the element l_1 is repeated, and then we can say that the element
110 l_1 has neutrosophic multiplicity 3 with different neutrosophic components.

111 If the element l_1 is repeated times with the same neutrosophic comonents, we say l_1 has
112 multiplicity. If the element l_1 is repeated times with different neutrosophic comonents, we say
113 l_1 has the neutrosophic multiplicity (nm).the nm function can be defined as follow:

$$114 \quad nm: X \rightarrow N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, \infty\} \text{ for any } r \in R$$

$$115 \quad nm(r) = \{(p_1, \langle T_1, I_1, F_1 \rangle), (p_2, \langle T_2, I_2, F_2 \rangle), \dots, (p_i, \langle T_i, I_i, F_i \rangle), \dots\},$$

116 which means that r is repeated by p_1 times with the neutrosophic components $\langle T_1, I_1, F_1 \rangle$; r is
117 repeated by p_2 times with the neutrosophic components $\langle T_2, I_2, F_2 \rangle$; ...; r is repeated by p_i
118 times with the neutrosophic components $\langle T_i, I_i, F_i \rangle$; and so on. $p_1, p_2, \dots, p_i, \dots \in N$,
119 and $\langle T_j, I_j, F_j \rangle \neq \langle T_k, I_k, F_k \rangle$, for $j \neq k$ and $j, k \in N$. Then a neutrosophic multiset R can be
120 written as:

$$121 \quad (R, nm(r)) \text{ or } \{(r, nm(r)) \text{ , for } r \in R\} \quad (6)$$

122 Now, with respect to the previous neutrosophic multisets K, L , we compute the
123 neutrosophic multiplicity function:

124 $nm_K: K \rightarrow N;$
 125 $nm_K(k_1) = \{(3, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle)\};$
 126 $nm_K(k_2) = \{(1, \langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.1 \rangle)\};$
 127 $nm_L: L \rightarrow N;$
 128 $nm_L(l_1) = \{(1, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.8, 0.1, 0.1 \rangle)\};$
 129 $nm_L(l_2) = \{(1, \langle 0.6, 0.4, 0.1 \rangle)\}.$

130 3. Single Valued Neutrosophic Multiset

131 **Definition 4.** Let X be a space of points (objects) with a generic element x in X and $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, \infty\}$.
 132 A SVN R in X can be defined as follows:

133 $R = \{x, ((p_{R1}, \langle T_{R1}(x), I_{R1}(x), F_{R1}(x) \rangle), (p_{R2}, \langle T_{R2}(x), I_{R2}(x), F_{R2}(x) \rangle), \dots, (p_{Rj}, \langle T_{Rj}(x), I_{Rj}(x), F_{Rj}(x) \rangle)) | x \in$
 134 $X\},$

135 **where** $T_{Rk}(x), I_{Rk}(x), F_{Rk}(x)$ express the truth-membership function, the
 136 indeterminacy-membership function and the falsity-membership function, respectively.
 137 $T_{R1}(x), T_{R2}(x), \dots, T_{Rk}(x) \in [0, 1], I_{R1}(x), I_{R2}(x), \dots, I_{Rk}(x) \in [0, 1], F_{R1}(x), F_{R2}(x), \dots, F_{Rk}(x) \in [0, 1]$
 138 and $0 \leq T_{Rk}(x) + I_{Rk}(x) + F_{Rk}(x) \leq 3$, for $k=1, 2, \dots, j, j \in N, p_{R1}, p_{R2}, \dots, p_{Rj} \in N$ and $p_{R1} +$
 139 $p_{R2} + \dots + p_{Rj} \geq 2$.

140 For convenience, a SVN R can be denoted by the following simplified form:

141 $R = \{x, (p_{Rk}, \langle T_{Rk}(x), I_{Rk}(x), F_{Rk}(x) \rangle) | x \in X\},$ for $k=1, 2, \dots, j$.

142 For example, with a universal set $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, a SVN R is given as:

143 $R = \{(x_1, (2, \langle 0.6, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.2 \rangle)), (x_2, (1, \langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle), (2, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle))\}.$

144 Then

145 $nm_R(x_1) = \{(2, \langle 0.6, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.2 \rangle)\};$

146 $nm_R(x_2) = \{(1, \langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle), (2, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle)\}.$

147 **Definition 5.** Let X be a space of points (objects) with a generic element x in X , M and L be two
 148 SVNMs,

149 $M = \{x, (p_{Mk}, \langle T_{Mk}(x), I_{Mk}(x), F_{Mk}(x) \rangle) | x \in X\},$ for $k=1, 2, \dots, j$,

150 $L = \{x, (p_{Lk}, \langle T_{Lk}(x), I_{Lk}(x), F_{Lk}(x) \rangle) | x \in X\},$ for $k=1, 2, \dots, j$,

151 **then** the relations of them are given as follows:

152 ① $M = L$, if and only if $p_{Mk} = p_{Lk}, T_{Mk}(x) = T_{Lk}(x), I_{Mk}(x) = I_{Lk}(x), F_{Mk}(x) = F_{Lk}(x)$, for
 153 $k=1, 2, \dots, j$;

154 ② $M \cup L = \{x, ((p_{Mk} \vee p_{Lk}), \langle T_{Mk}(x) \vee T_{Lk}(x), I_{Mk}(x) \wedge I_{Lk}(x), F_{Mk}(x) \wedge F_{Lk}(x) \rangle) | x \in X\}$ for $k =$
 155 $1, 2, \dots, j$;

156 ③ $M \cap L = \{x, ((p_{Mk} \wedge p_{Lk}), \langle T_{Mk}(x) \wedge T_{Lk}(x), I_{Mk}(x) \vee I_{Lk}(x), F_{Mk}(x) \vee F_{Lk}(x) \rangle) | x \in$
 157 $X\},$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, j$.

158 For convenience, we can use $r =$
 159 $((p_{r1}, \langle T_{r1}(x), I_{r1}(x), F_{r1}(x) \rangle), (p_{r2}, \langle T_{r2}(x), I_{r2}(x), F_{r2}(x) \rangle), \dots, (p_{rj}, \langle T_{rj}(x), I_{rj}(x), F_{rj}(x) \rangle))$ to express a basic element in a
 160 SVN R and call r a single valued neutrosophic multiset element (SVNME).

161 For example, with a universal set $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$, then two SVNMs M and L are given as:

162 $M = \{(x_1, (2, \langle 0.6, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.4, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle)), (x_2, (1, \langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle))\};$

163 $L = \{(x_1, (1, \langle 0.6, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle)), (x_2, (1, \langle 0.9, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle))\};$

164 $M \cup L$

165 $= \{(x_1, (2, \langle 0.6, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.4, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.8, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle)), (x_2, (1, \langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.9, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle))\}$

166 $M \cap L = \{x_1, (1, \langle 0.6, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle)\}.$

167 **Definition 6.** Let X be a space of points (objects) with a generic element x in X and M be a SVN M , we
 168 can change a SVN M into a SVNS \tilde{M} by using the operational rules of SVNS.

169
$$M = \{x, (p_{Mk}, \langle T_{Mk}(x), I_{Mk}(x), F_{Mk}(x) \rangle) | x \in X\}, \text{ for } k = 1, 2, \dots, j.$$

170 Then

171
$$\tilde{M} = \{x, 1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} | x \in X\}. \quad (7)$$

172 **Proof:**

173 Set m_1, m_2, \dots, m_j are basic elements in M .

174 When $k=1$, we can get

175 $m_1 = (\langle T_{m1}(x), I_{m1}(x), F_{m1}(x) \rangle, \langle T_{m1}(x), I_{m1}(x), F_{m1}(x) \rangle, \dots, \langle T_{m1}(x), I_{m1}(x), F_{m1}(x) \rangle),$ which
 176 has neutrosophic multiplicity p_{m1} .

177 According to the operational rules of SVNSs, we can get:

178 $+m_1=1 - (1 - T_{m1}(x))^{p_{m1}}, (I_{m1}(x))^{p_{m1}}, (F_{m1}(x))^{p_{m1}}.$

179 As the same reason, when $k=2$, we can get

180 $+m_2=1 - (1 - T_{m2}(x))^{p_{m2}}, (I_{m1}(x))^{p_{m2}}, (F_{m2}(x))^{p_{m2}}.$

181 Then

182 $m_1+m_2 = 1 - (1 - T_{m1}(x))^{p_{m1}} (1 -$

183 $T_{m2}(x))^{p_{m2}}, (I_{m1}(x))^{p_{m1}} (I_{m1}(x))^{p_{m2}}, (F_{m2}(x))^{p_{m1}} (F_{m2}(x))^{p_{m2}}$

184 $= 1 - \prod_{k=1}^2 (1 - T_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}, \prod_{k=1}^2 (I_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}, \prod_{k=1}^2 (F_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}};$

185 Suppose when $k=i$, the formula (7) is established, then we can get:

186 $m_1+m_2 + \dots + m_i=1 - \prod_{k=1}^i (1 - T_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}, \prod_{k=1}^i (I_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}, \prod_{k=1}^i (F_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}};$

187 Then

188 $m_1+m_2 + \dots + m_i + m_{i+1} = 1 - \prod_{k=1}^i (1 - T_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}} + 1 - (1 - T_{m(i+1)}(x))^{p_{m(i+1)}} - (1 - \prod_{k=1}^i (1 -$

189 $T_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}})(1 - (1 -$

190 $T_{m(i+1)}(x))^{p_{m(i+1)}}), (\prod_{k=1}^i (I_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}) (I_{m(i+1)}(x))^{p_{m(i+1)}}, (\prod_{k=1}^i (F_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}) (F_{m(i+1)}(x))^{p_{m(i+1)}}$

191 $= 1 - \prod_{k=1}^{i+1} (1 - T_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}, \prod_{k=1}^{i+1} (I_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}, \prod_{k=1}^{i+1} (F_{mk}(x))^{p_{mk}}.$

192 To sum up, when $k = i+1$, the formula (7) is true, and then according to the mathematical
 193 induction, we can get that the aggregation result is also true.

194 **Definition 7.** Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ be a universe of discourse, and M and N be two SVN M s, and
 195 then the operational rules of SVN M s are defined as follows:

196 $M = \{x, (p_{Mk}, \langle T_{Mk}(x), I_{Mk}(x), F_{Mk}(x) \rangle) | x \in X\}, \text{ for } k=1, 2, \dots, j;$

197 $N = \{x, (p_{Nk}, \langle T_{Nk}(x), I_{Nk}(x), F_{Nk}(x) \rangle) | x \in X\}, \text{ for } k = 1, 2, \dots, j;$

198 $M \oplus N$

199 $= \{x, 1$

200 $- \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \prod_{k=1}^j (1$

201 $- T_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}} | x \in X\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
202 \quad M \otimes N &= \{ \langle x, \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \right) \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}} \right), \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \\
203 \quad &+ \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \\
204 \quad &+ \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}} \rangle | x \in X \} \\
205 \quad \varphi M &= \{ \langle x, \left(1 - \left(\prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \right)^\varphi \right), \left(\prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \right)^\varphi, \left(\prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}} \right)^\varphi \rangle | x \in X \} \\
206 \quad M^\varphi &= \{ \langle x, \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \right)^\varphi, 1 - \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x))^{p_{Mk}} \right)^\varphi, 1 \\
207 \quad &- \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Nk}(x))^{p_{Nk}} \right)^\varphi \rangle | x \in X \}
\end{aligned}$$

208 4. Cosine Measures of Single Value Neutrosophic Multisets

209 Cosine measures are usually used in science and engineering applications. In this section,
210 we propose a cosine measure of SVNMs and a weighted cosine measure of SVNMs.

211 **Definition 8.** Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ be a universe of discourse, M and N be two SVNMs,

$$\begin{aligned}
212 \quad M &= \\
213 \quad &\{ \langle x_i, (p_{M1}, \langle T_{M1}(x_i), I_{M1}(x_i), F_{M1}(x_i) \rangle), (p_{M2}, \langle T_{M2}(x_i), I_{M2}(x_i), F_{M2}(x_i) \rangle), \dots, (p_{Mj}, \langle T_{Mj}(x_i), I_{Mj}(x_i), F_{Mj}(x_i) \rangle) \rangle | x_i \in \\
214 \quad &X \}, \\
215 \quad N &= \\
216 \quad &\{ \langle x_i, (p_{N1}, \langle T_{N1}(x_i), I_{N1}(x_i), F_{N1}(x_i) \rangle), (p_{N2}, \langle T_{N2}(x_i), I_{N2}(x_i), F_{N2}(x_i) \rangle), \dots, (p_{Nj}, \langle T_{Nj}(x_i), I_{Nj}(x_i), F_{Nj}(x_i) \rangle) \rangle | x_i \\
217 \quad &\in X \}
\end{aligned}$$

218 Then, a cosine measure between two SVNMs M and N is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
219 \quad \rho(M, N) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left| \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{p_{Mk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{p_{Nk}} \right| \right. \\
220 \quad &+ \left| \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x_i))^{p_{Mk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Nk}(x_i))^{p_{Nk}} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Mk}(x_i))^{p_{Mk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Nk}(x_i))^{p_{Nk}} \right| \left. \right\} \\
221 \quad & \quad \quad \quad (8)
\end{aligned}$$

222 **Theorem 1.** The cosine measure $\rho(M, N)$ between two SVNMs M and N satisfies the following
223 properties:

- 224 ① $\rho(M, N) = \rho(N, M)$;
- 225 ② $0 \leq \rho(M, N) \leq 1$;
- 226 ③ $\rho(M, N) = 1$, if and only if $M = N$.

227 **Proof** ①:

228 For $|\prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| + |\prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} -$
 229 $\prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| + |\prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| = |\prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} -$
 230 $\prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk}| + |\prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk}| + |\prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} -$
 231 $\prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk}|$, so we can get $\rho(M, N) = \rho(N, M)$.

232 ⊙:

233 For $0 \leq T_{Mk}(x_i) \leq 1, 0 \leq I_{Mk}(x_i) \leq 1, 0 \leq F_{Mk}(x_i) \leq 1, 0 \leq T_{Nk}(x_i) \leq 1, 0 \leq I_{Nk}(x_i) \leq$
 234 $1, 0 \leq F_{Nk}(x_i) \leq 1$;

235 Then we can get

236 $0 \leq 1 - T_{Mk}(x_i) \leq 1$ and $0 \leq 1 - T_{Nk}(x_i) \leq 1$;

237 $0 \leq \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \leq 1$;

238 So,

239 $0 \leq |\prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| \leq 1$.

240 As the same reason, we can get

241 $0 \leq |\prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| \leq 1$ and $0 \leq |\prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} -$
 242 $\prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| \leq 1$

243 Above all, we can get $0 \leq |\prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| +$
 244 $|\prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| + |\prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk}| \leq 3$ and $0 \leq$

245 $\sum_{i=1}^n \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} -$

246 $\prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| \leq 1$;

247 $\rho(M, N) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| \right.$

248 $\left. + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| \right\}$

249 $= \frac{1}{n} \left(\cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left(\left| \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_1))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_1))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_1))^{pMk} -$

250 $\prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_1))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_1))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_1))^{pNk} \right| \right) + \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left(\left| \prod_{k=1}^j(1 -$

251 $T_{Mk}(x_2))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_2))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_2))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_2))^{pNk} \right| +$

252 $\left| \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_2))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_2))^{pNk} \right| \right) + \dots + \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left(\left| \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_n))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 -$

253 $T_{Nk}(x_n))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_n))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_n))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_n))^{pMk} -$

254 $\prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_n))^{pNk} \right| \right)$.

255 Let $\cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left(\left| \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} -$

256 $\prod_{k=1}^j(I_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(F_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| \right) = a_i$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$), then

257 $\rho(M, N) = \frac{1}{n} \{a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n\}$.

258 According to $0 \leq \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left(\left| \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{pMk} - \prod_{k=1}^j(1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{pNk} \right| +$

$$259 \quad \left| \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x_i))^{p_{Mk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Nk}(x_i))^{p_{Nk}} \right| + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Mk}(x_i))^{p_{Mk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Nk}(x_i))^{p_{Nk}} \right| \} = a_i \leq 1 \quad ,$$

260 we can obtain $0 \leq a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n \leq n$ and $0 \leq \frac{1}{n}(a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n) \leq 1$, so we can get $0 \leq$

261 $\rho(M, N) \leq 1$.

262 ③ If $M=N$ then $T_{Mk}(x_i) = T_{Nk}(x_i)$, $I_{Mk}(x_i) = I_{Nk}(x_i)$, and $F_{Mk}(x_i) = F_{Nk}(x_i)$ for any $x_i \in$
263 X and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, so we can get $\rho(M, N) = 1$, if and only if $M = N$.

264 Now, we consider different weights for each element $x_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ in X . Then, let $w =$
265 $(w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ be the **weight** vector of each element $x_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ with $w_i \in [0, 1]$,
266 and $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$. Hence, we further extend the cosine measure of Equation (8) to the following
267 weighted cosine measure of SVNMs:

$$268 \quad \rho_w(M, N) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} \left(\left| \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Mk}(x_i))^{p_{Mk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{Nk}(x_i))^{p_{Nk}} \right| \right. \right.$$

$$269 \quad \left. \left. + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Mk}(x_i))^{p_{Mk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{Nk}(x_i))^{p_{Nk}} \right| \right. \right.$$

$$270 \quad \left. \left. + \left| \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Mk}(x_i))^{p_{Mk}} - \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{Nk}(x_i))^{p_{Nk}} \right| \right) \right\}$$

271 (9)

272 **Theorem 2.** The cosine measure $\rho_w(M, N)$ between two SVNMs M and N satisfies the following
273 properties:

274 ① $\rho_w(M, N) = \rho_w(N, M)$;

275 ② $0 \leq \rho_w(M, N) \leq 1$;

276 ③ $\rho_w(M, N) = 1$, if and only if $M = N$.

277 The proof of Theorem 2 is similar to **that of** the **Theorem 1**, so we omitted it here.

278 5. Cosine Measure of SVNMs for Multiple Attribute Decision-making

279 In this section, we use the weighted cosine measure of SVNMs to deal with the multiple
280 attribute decision-making problems with SVNMs information.

281 Let $G = \{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_m\}$ as a set of alternatives and $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ as a set of
282 attributes, then they can be established in a decision-making problem. But **sometimes**
283 $x_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ maybe have multiplicity, and then we can use the form of a SVNMs to
284 represent the evaluation value.

285 Let $g_r =$

286 $\{x_i, (p_{g_r,1}, \langle T_{g_r,1}(x_i), I_{g_r,1}(x_i), F_{g_r,1}(x_i) \rangle), (p_{g_r,2}, \langle T_{g_r,2}(x_i), I_{g_r,2}(x_i), F_{g_r,2}(x_i) \rangle), \dots, (p_{g_r,j}, \langle T_{g_r,j}(x_i), I_{g_r,j}(x_i), F_{g_r,j}(x_i) \rangle) \mid x_i \in$
287 $X\}$, for $r=1, 2, \dots, m$ and $i=1, 2, \dots, n$. Then we can establish the SVNMs decision matrix D , which is
288 shown in Table 1.

289 **Table 1.** The SVNMs decision matrix D

		x_1	...
g_1	$x_1, (p_{g_1,1}, \langle T_{g_1,1}(x_1), I_{g_1,1}(x_1), F_{g_1,1}(x_1) \rangle), \dots, (p_{g_1,j}, \langle T_{g_1,j}(x_1), I_{g_1,j}(x_1), F_{g_1,j}(x_1) \rangle)$...

g_2	$x_1, (p_{g_2 1}, \langle T_{g_2 1}(x_1), I_{g_2 1}(x_1), F_{g_2 1}(x_1) \rangle), \dots, (p_{g_2 j}, \langle T_{g_2 j}(x_1), I_{g_2 j}(x_1), F_{g_2 j}(x_1) \rangle)$...
...
g_m	$x_1, (p_{g_m 1}, \langle T_{g_m 1}(x_1), I_{g_m 1}(x_1), F_{g_m 1}(x_1) \rangle), \dots, (p_{g_m j}, \langle T_{g_m j}(x_1), I_{g_m j}(x_1), F_{g_m j}(x_1) \rangle)$...

x_n		
x_n	$(p_{g_1 1}, \langle T_{g_1 1}(x_n), I_{g_1 1}(x_n), F_{g_1 1}(x_n) \rangle), \dots, (p_{g_1 j}, \langle T_{g_1 j}(x_n), I_{g_1 j}(x_n), F_{g_1 j}(x_n) \rangle)$	
x_n	$(p_{g_2 1}, \langle T_{g_2 1}(x_n), I_{g_2 1}(x_n), F_{g_2 1}(x_n) \rangle), \dots, (p_{g_2 j}, \langle T_{g_2 j}(x_n), I_{g_2 j}(x_n), F_{g_2 j}(x_n) \rangle)$	
...	...	
x_n	$(p_{g_m 1}, \langle T_{g_m 1}(x_n), I_{g_m 1}(x_n), F_{g_m 1}(x_n) \rangle), \dots, (p_{g_m j}, \langle T_{g_m j}(x_n), I_{g_m j}(x_n), F_{g_m j}(x_n) \rangle)$	

290 **Step 1:** By using the Equation (7), we change the SVN decision matrix D into SVNS
 291 decision matrix \tilde{D} , which is shown in Table 2.

292 **Table 2.** The SVNS decision matrix \tilde{D}

	x_1	...
\tilde{g}_1	$\langle x_1, 1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{g_1 k}(x_1))^{p_{g_1 k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{g_1 k}(x_1))^{p_{g_1 k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{g_1 k}(x_1))^{p_{g_1 k}} \rangle$...
\tilde{g}_2	$\langle x_1, 1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{g_2 k}(x_1))^{p_{g_2 k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{g_2 k}(x_1))^{p_{g_2 k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{g_2 k}(x_1))^{p_{g_2 k}} \rangle$...
...
\tilde{g}_m	$\langle x_1, 1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{g_m k}(x_1))^{p_{g_m k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{g_m k}(x_1))^{p_{g_m k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{g_m k}(x_1))^{p_{g_m k}} \rangle$...

x_n		
	$\langle x_n, 1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{g_1 k}(x_n))^{p_{g_1 k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{g_1 k}(x_n))^{p_{g_1 k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{g_1 k}(x_n))^{p_{g_1 k}} \rangle$	
	$\langle x_n, 1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{g_2 k}(x_n))^{p_{g_2 k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{g_2 k}(x_n))^{p_{g_2 k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{g_2 k}(x_n))^{p_{g_2 k}} \rangle$	
	...	
	$\langle x_n, 1 - \prod_{k=1}^j (1 - T_{g_m k}(x_n))^{p_{g_m k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (I_{g_m k}(x_n))^{p_{g_m k}}, \prod_{k=1}^j (F_{g_m k}(x_n))^{p_{g_m k}} \rangle$	

293 **Step 2:** Setting $T_{g^*}(x_i)$ is the maximum truth value in each
 294 column x_i of the decision matrix \tilde{D} , $I_{g^*}(x_i)$ and $F_{g^*}(x_i)$ are the minimum indeterminate and
 295 falsity values in each column x_i of the decision matrix \tilde{D} , **respectively**, the ideal solution can be
 296 determined as x_i^* .

297
$$x_i^* = \langle T_{g^*}(x_i), I_{g^*}(x_i), F_{g^*}(x_i) \rangle, \text{ for } i=1, 2, \dots, n.$$

298 So we can get the ideal alternative $g^* = \{x_1^*, x_2^*, \dots, x_n^*\}$.

299 **Step 3:** When the **weight** vector of attributes for the different importance of each attribute

300 $x_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ is given by $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ with $w_i \geq 0$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$. Then, we utilize

301 the weighted cosine measure **to deal with** multiple attribute decision-making problems with

302 SVNMs information. The weighted cosine measure between an alternative $\tilde{g}_r (r = 1, 2, \dots, m)$

303 and the ideal alternative g^* can be calculated by using the following formula:

$$304 \rho_w(g_r, g^*) = \rho_w(\tilde{g}_r, g^*) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cos \left\{ \frac{\pi}{6} (|T_{\tilde{g}_r}(x_i) - T_{g^*}(x_i)| + |I_{\tilde{g}_r}(x_i) - I_{g^*}(x_i)| + |F_{\tilde{g}_r}(x_i) -$$

$$305 F_{g^*}(x_i)|) \right\}.$$

306 (10)

307 **Step 4:** According to the values of $\rho_w(\tilde{g}_r, g^*)$ for $r=1, 2, \dots, m$, we rank the alternatives

308 and select the best one.

309 **Step 5:** End.

310 The formalization of the steps is illustrated in Fig. 1.

311 **Fig. 1.** Flowchart of the decision steps

312 6. Numerical Example and Comparative Analysis

313 6.1 Numerical Example

314 Now, we utilize a practical example for the decision-making problem adapted from the

315 literature [21] to demonstrate the applications of the proposed method under a SVNMs

316 environment. Now, one customer wants to buy a car, he selects four types of cars and

317 evaluates them according to four attributes. Then, we build a decision model. There are four

318 possible alternatives (g_1, g_2, g_3, g_4) to be considered. **Decision should be taken** according to

319 four attributes: fuel economy (x_1) , price (x_2) , comfort (x_3) , safety (x_4) . The **weight** vector of

320 these four attributes is given by $w = (0.5, 0.25, 0.125, 0.125)^T$. Then, the customer tests the four

321 cars on the road with less obstacles and on the road with more obstacles, respectively, and

322 after testing, some attributes may have two different evaluated values or the same. So the

323 customer evaluates the four cars (alternatives) under the four attributes by the form of

324 SVNMs.

325 **Step 1:** Establish the SVN decision matrix D provided by the customer, which is given
 326 as the following SVN decision matrix D in Tables 3.

327 **Table 3.** The SVN decision matrix D

	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4
g_1	$(1, \langle 0.5, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.6 \rangle)$	$1, \langle 0.4, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle$	$(1, \langle 0.7, 0.7, 0.5 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.8, 0.7, 0.6 \rangle)$	$(1, \langle 0.1, 0.5, 0.7 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.5, 0.2, 0.8 \rangle)$
g_2	$(1, \langle 0.9, 0.7, 0.5 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.7, 0.7, 0.1 \rangle)$	$1, \langle 0.7, 0.6, 0.8 \rangle$	$2, \langle 0.9, 0.4, 0.6 \rangle$	$(1, \langle 0.5, 0.2, 0.7 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.5, 0.1, 0.9 \rangle)$
g_3	$(1, \langle 0.3, 0.4, 0.2 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.6, 0.3, 0.7 \rangle)$	$1, \langle 0.2, 0.2, 0.2 \rangle$	$(1, \langle 0.9, 0.5, 0.5 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.6, 0.5, 0.2 \rangle)$	$(1, \langle 0.7, 0.5, 0.3 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.4, 0.2, 0.2 \rangle)$
g_4	$(1, \langle 0.9, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.8, 0.6, 0.1 \rangle)$	$1, \langle 0.3, 0.5, 0.2 \rangle$	$(1, \langle 0.5, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle), (1, \langle 0.1, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle)$	$2, \langle 0.4, 0.2, 0.8 \rangle$

328 **Step 2:** By using the Equation (7), we change the SVN decision matrix D into SVNS
 329 decision matrix \tilde{D} , which is shown in Table 4.

330 **Table 4.** The SVNS decision matrix \tilde{D}

	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4
\tilde{g}_1	$\langle 0.85, 0.21, 0.12 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.4, 0.5 \rangle$	$\langle 0.94, 0.49, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.55, 0.1, 0.56 \rangle$
\tilde{g}_2	$\langle 0.97, 0.49, 0.05 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.6, 0.8 \rangle$	$\langle 0.99, 0.16, 0.36 \rangle$	$\langle 0.75, 0.02, 0.63 \rangle$
\tilde{g}_3	$\langle 0.72, 0.12, 0.14 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.2, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.96, 0.25, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.82, 0.1, 0.06 \rangle$
\tilde{g}_4	$\langle 0.98, 0.42, 0.02 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.5, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.55, 0.28, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.64, 0.04, 0.64 \rangle$

331 **Step 3:** According to the decision matrix \tilde{D} , we can get the ideal alternative g^* :

332
$$g^* = \{ \langle 0.98, 0.12, 0.02 \rangle \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.2 \rangle \langle 0.99, 0.16, 0.1 \rangle \langle 0.82, 0.02, 0.06 \rangle \}.$$

333 **Step 4:** By applying the Equation (10), we can obtain the values of the weighted cosine
 334 measure between each alternative and the ideal alternative g^* as follows:

335
$$\rho_w(g_1, g^*) = 0.9535, \rho_w(g_2, g^*) = 0.9511, \rho_w(g_3, g^*) = 0.9813 \text{ and } \rho_w(g_4, g^*) = 0.9616.$$

336 **Step 5:** According to the above values of weighted cosine measure, we can rank the four
 337 alternatives: $g_3 > g_4 > g_1 > g_2$. Therefore, the alternative g_3 is the best choice.

338 This example clearly indicates that the proposed decision-making method based on the
 339 weighted cosine measure of SVNMs is relatively simple and easy for dealing with multiple
 340 attribute decision-making problems under SVN environment.

341 **6.2 Comparative Analysis**

342 In what follows, we compare the proposed method for SVN with other existing related
 343 methods for SVN, all the results are shown in Table 5.

344 **Table 5.** The ranking orders by utilizing four different methods

Method	Result	Ranking order	The best alternative
Method 1 based on correlation coefficient in [11]	$\rho_w(g_1, g^*)=0.9053,$ $\rho_w(g_2, g^*) = 0.9017,$ $\rho_w(g_3, g^*) = 0.9516,$ $\rho_w(g_4, g^*) = 0.8816.$	$g_3 > g_1 > g_2 > g_4$	g_3

Method 2 based on similarity in [16]	$\rho_w(g_1, g^*)=0.8204,$ $\rho_w(g_2, g^*) =0.8108,$ $\rho_w(g_3, g^*) =0.8867,$ $\rho_w(g_4, g^*) =0.8358.$	$g_3 \succ g_4 \succ g_2 \succ g_1$	g_3
Method 3 based on similarity in [16]	$\rho_w(g_1, g^*)=0.7898,$ $\rho_w(g_2, g^*) =0.7121,$ $\rho_w(g_3, g^*) =0.8125,$ $\rho_w(g_4, g^*) =0.7553.$	$g_3 \succ g_1 \succ g_4 \succ g_2$	g_3
The proposed method	$\rho_w(g_1, g^*)=0.9535,$ $\rho_w(g_2, g^*) =0.9511,$ $\rho_w(g_3, g^*) =0.9813,$ $\rho_w(g_4, g^*) =9616.$	$g_3 \succ g_4 \succ g_1 \succ g_2$	g_3

345 From Table 5, these four methods have the same best alternative g_3 . Many methods such
 346 as similarity measure, correlation coefficient, and cosine measure can all be used in SVNМ to
 347 handle the multiple attribute decision-making problems and can get the similar results.

348 The proposed decision-making method can express and handle the multiplicity evaluated
 349 data given by decision makers or experts, while various existing neutrosophic
 350 decision-making methods cannot deal with these problems.

351 **7. Conclusions**

352 Based on the multiplicity evaluation in some real situations, this paper introduced a
 353 SVNМ as a subclass of NM to express the multiplicity information and the operational
 354 relations of SVNMs. The SVNМ is expressed by its one or more elements, which may have
 355 multiplicity. Therefore, SVNМ has the desirable advantages and characteristics of expressing
 356 and handling the multiplicity problems, while existing neutrosophic sets cannot deal with
 357 them.

358 Then, we proposed the cosine measure of SVNMs and weighted cosine measure of
 359 SVNMs and investigated their properties. Based on the weighted cosine measure of SVNMs,
 360 the multiple attribute decision-making methods under SVNМ environments was proposed, in
 361 which the evaluated values were taken the form of SVNMEs. Through the weighed cosine
 362 measure between each alternative and the ideal alternative, one can determine the ranking
 363 order of all alternatives and can select the best one. Finally, a practical example adapted from
 364 the literature [21] about buying cars was presented to demonstrate the effectiveness and
 365 practicality of the proposed method in this paper. According to the ranking orders, we can find
 366 that the ranking result with weighted cosine measures is agreement with the ranking results in
 367 literature [21]. Then the proposed method is suitable for actual applications in multiple
 368 attribute decision-making problems with single value neutrosophic multiplicity information.

369 In the future, we shall extend SVNMs to interval neutrosophic multisets and develop the
 370 application of interval neutrosophic multisets for handling the decision-making methods or
 371 other domains.

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